

LIFE-BECKON proposal for Transition Living Labs

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Abstract

This paper discusses the importance of energy communities in the transition to renewable energy and how the LIFE-BECKON project is supporting their development through a comprehensive support mechanism, including a Technical Assistance Cookbook, Capacity Building program, and One-Stop-Shop platform. The role of Transition Living Labs in facilitating the development and scaling up of Energy Communities is also explored, with a focus on the Transition Living Lab created by LIFE-BECKON to validate its support mechanisms.

Key words

Energy Communities, One-Stop-Shop, Technical Assistance, Transition Living

Introduction

Energy communities are an innovative and increasingly popular approach to promote the energy transition. They represent a paradigm shift from the traditional centralized energy system towards a more decentralized, democratic, and community-driven one. Energy communities enable citizens to take an active role in shaping their energy future, by promoting local ownership, collective decision-making, and mutual benefit. By involving citizens in the planning, development, and management of renewable energy projects, energy communities can enhance public acceptance, generate social and economic benefits, and contribute to the achievement of national and international climate goals.

The LIFE-BECKON project aims to boost the deployment of Energy Communities across Europe by developing and delivering comprehensive support mechanisms for public authorities, promoters, and local action groups. The project is focused on the Green Transition, which emphasizes the transition towards a more sustainable and environmentally friendly society.

The project's comprehensive support mechanism includes a Technical Assistance Cookbook to enable the creation of Technical Assistance Offices, a Capacity Building program via Train the Trainer approach to increase stakeholder knowledge, and integrated services via a One-Stop-Shop platform to facilitate access to information, tools, and guides as well as matchmaking among actors along the value chain.

The LIFE-BECKON project is well-aligned with the Living Labs approach focused on creating sustainable impact through iterative feedback processes and co-creation among stakeholders. The services via One-Stop-Shop platform operate as intermediaries among citizens, research organizations, companies, and government agencies, and provide comprehensive support mechanisms to facilitate the creation of Energy Communities.

Importance of Energy Communities

Most efforts to promote renewable energy have traditionally come from a top-down approach, where governments commit to certain goals by specific deadlines without considering the necessary value chains. While setting national goals and passing legislation are essential to incite climate action, a bottom-up approach can also be effective (Prina, Matteo Giacomo, et al., 2020). In areas where government accountability is lacking, citizens can demand national action and embrace the energy transition independently of the national agenda.

Currently, there are over 9,000 energy community initiatives across Europe. Renewable energy communities have been shown to significantly influence public opinion in favor of renewable energy projects. For example, a case study in Germany revealed that the presence of energy communities reduced the percentage of negative opinions towards renewable energy from 60% to just 12% (Musall & Kuik, 2011). This remarkable shift can be attributed to the local ownership aspect of energy communities, which enhances public acceptance of renewables by reversing the "not in my backyard" mentality (Commission Staff Working Document Impact Assessment, 2016).

By using a simultaneous top-down and bottom-up approach, we can help reach net-zero goals while improving public opinion (Koopmans & Velde, 2001). Governments can set national goals and create the legal framework necessary to support renewable energy initiatives, while citizens can take an active role in promoting energy communities and demanding change. Together, this collaborative approach can foster a more sustainable energy system, empower communities, and transform our world (Dai, *et. al.*, 2015).

Role of Transition Living Labs in Energy Communities

In the context of Energy Communities, Transition Living Labs can facilitate the development and testing of new energy technologies, business models, and governance structures. They can provide a platform for collaboration among stakeholders and help to build trust and social capital, which is essential for the success of Energy Communities. Transition Living Labs can also help to identify and address potential barriers to the development of Energy Communities, such as regulatory and policy constraints, technical challenges, and market barriers.

Moreover, Transition Living Labs can play a key role in the scaling up of Energy Communities. By providing a platform for testing and validation of Energy Community solutions, Transition Living Labs can help to build evidence and momentum for wider adoption of these solutions. They can also facilitate the dissemination and replication of successful Energy Community models across different geographical areas and market contexts.

LIFE-BECKON's Transition Living Lab

The Transition Living Lab is focused on validating the comprehensive support mechanisms developed by LIFE-BECKON (LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM-LIFE-BECKON, 2023) to promote the creation of Energy Communities. This validation will be made with pilot's

Technical Assistance Offices, citizens open places with tailored training material on how to develop an EC and how to use the One-Stop-Shop (OSS) with more in-depth tools and resources. Embodying a Living Lab approach, the content will address the specific needs of these pilot offices that are currently unfulfilled by existing tools. Surveys and interviews are being conducted in these pilot areas to hear exactly from the future users what needs are left unmet.

These mechanisms include a Technical Assistance cookbook, Capacity Building program, and One-Stop-Shop platform. The Technical Assistance cookbook enables the creation of Technical Assistance Offices, while the Capacity Building program uses a Train the Trainer approach to increase stakeholder knowledge. The One-Stop-Shop platform facilitates access to information, tools, and guides, as well as matchmaking among actors along the value chain.

Technical Assistance Cookbook

The purpose of the Cookbook is to outline the technical steps and the administrative steps (financial, legal, participatory, etc.) with corresponding tools to simplify the process for project promoters. Both categories of steps (technical and administrative) are divided into four distinct phases: initiation, design, implementation, and operation. This is to ensure the user is working on both types of tasks in parallel. The Cookbook is set up as a roadmap that starts with an initial placement quiz to determine the stage of the project to filter out the already accomplished steps. It is designed so that someone with little technical expertise can navigate the Cookbook, understand each of the steps, and make use of the tools. At this point, the steps of the Cookbook have been defined, and a gap analysis is underway to identify which existing tools to leverage and which must be developed or modified. This Cookbook will be available on the OSS.

Capacity Building Program

This capacity building program will equip project promoters (public authorities, energy agencies, local action groups, energy companies) with the knowledge they need to confidently lead an energy community initiative. A "train the trainers" approach will be implemented at the three pilot sites to create a ripple effect. The goal is to heighten community energy awareness amongst local stakeholders, thereby encouraging them to spread the enthusiasm across their region. This approach follows a Living Labs methodology; with the citizens involved at all stages, and the program is constantly evolving to meet their needs. As of now, hundreds of actors across the three different pilot

sites have been surveyed or interviewed to perform a needs analysis and learn how best to tailor the various resources. Preliminary results have shown that all pilot sites need support regarding financial management at a project level and individual level.

Additionally, the capacity building program will include a series of interactive training. These will include videos to complement the Cookbook, physical workshops to facilitate relationships across the value chain in each region, and webinars to support EC deployment. The recorded resources will be made available on the Training Hub of the OSS.

Integrated Services via One-Stop-Shop Platform

The OSS will be composed of a Knowledge Hub, a Training Hub, and an Opportunities Hub. The Knowledge Hub will host the Cookbook and a bibliography with useful resources. These resources will include those referenced by the Cookbook and other tools that could be useful for audiences other than EC promoters. For example, there are tools to help citizens independently improve energy efficiency in their home or install solar panels on their roof (without being a part of an EC). The Training Hub will include the educational materials produced in the Capacity Building effort, described below. The Opportunity Hub acts as a matchmaking platform and will directly interface with the Cookbook in the Knowledge Hub. Specific technical and financial experts in each location are recommended at certain steps of the roadmap if extra support is deemed necessary. The Opportunity Hub also includes a forum where ECs can publish their project with the intention of finding investors, technical experts for specific problems, or starting a discussion.

Validation in demo areas

The support mechanisms will be validated in three supramunicipal areas in Avila-ES, Sofia-BG, and Copenhagen-DK, covering a wide range of conditions, cultural aspects, and market maturities. This diversity is necessary to ensure the robustness of the tools to maintain its applicability throughout the EU. The technical assistance offices or Transition Living Lab will educate actors local to the three pilot areas.

In general, the TAO pilots will interact with the existing local energy office to launch a call for projects. The target is to assist between a minimum of ten to a goal of twenty-five initiatives in each area. This assistance includes a Cookbook introduction session, a capacity building program throughout the area, and OSS engagement initiatives. The capacity building aims to reach 150 - 200 stakeholders in each pilot area, effectively

training the trainers and filling knowledge gaps.

After the launch of the pilot TAOs, the effectiveness and quality of the support mechanisms will be evaluated for certain indicators such as ease of use, robustness of features, and areas of improvement. The validation of the tools' efficacy is the most crucial step to guarantee the lasting impact of the implemented activities. The Living Labs evaluation and feedback of the tools will incite corrective actions to strengthen the Cookbook, Capacity Building program, and/or the One-Stop-Shop. These improvements will be implemented prior to the replication and dissemination activities to capitalise on the lessons learned from the pilot sites.

Conclusion

Energy Communities are gaining traction as an innovative approach to promote the energy transition, allowing citizens to take an active role in shaping their energy future by promoting local ownership, collective decision-making, and mutual benefit. The LIFE-BECKON project aims to boost the deployment of Energy Communities across Europe by developing and delivering comprehensive support mechanisms for public authorities, promoters, and local action groups. The project's comprehensive support mechanism includes a Technical Assistance Cookbook, Capacity Building program, and One-Stop-Shop platform.

The Transition Living Lab as Technical Assistance Offices developed in several municipalities across Europe are focused on validating the comprehensive support mechanisms developed by LIFE-BECKON to guarantee the quality before dissemination and replication. In the context of Energy Communities, this Transition Living Labs can facilitate the development and testing of new energy technologies, business models, and governance structures, and play a key role in the scaling up of Energy Communities.

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